

Diversity and Inclusion in Software Engineering Teaching

Hi there!

I'm collecting info and best practices about how diversity and inclusion (D&I) themes are approached in software engineering (SE) teaching. I would be more than happy if you could give your time and answer for this short questionnaire. Especially I'm really interested in what topics are already covered and how important SE teachers see diversity & inclusion themes in teaching!

You can always also send me an email and share more about your thoughts!

And please note—even though you don't feel that you are raising diversity and inclusion themes in your teaching, I would very much appreciate your answers—in fact, they would be really important for my research!

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About the Diversity & Inclusion:

Diversity means the representation of people with different backgrounds, from different cultures, ethnical groups, age groups, and different genders. Inclusion means that people with different backgrounds are welcomed and have access to participate and feel part of the group. In this short questionnaire I use "D&I" for Diversity & Inclusion and "SE" for Software Engineering.

This survey is anonymous. The data will be treated with respect, and the researcher will ensure the anonymity of the results.

1. In your SOFTWARE ENGINEERING course(s), which case examples/approaches of the diversity & inclusion you use the most in your TEACHING

Grading: Number 1 is the most used, number 2 second used etc.

Please note! Get number only for those approaches or case examples, which you use. You have to give number at least for one approach. Don't give number if you don't use that approach.

	<input type="radio"/>	1
	<input type="radio"/>	2
	<input type="radio"/>	3
	<input type="radio"/>	4
	<input type="radio"/>	5
Accessibility (Web accessibility, color, alt text etc.)	<input type="radio"/>	6
	<input type="radio"/>	7
	<input type="radio"/>	8
	<input type="radio"/>	9

10

1

2

3

4

5

Diverse teams (In projects, as a customers/end-users etc. - ethnicity, age, gender etc.)

6

7

8

9

10

1

2

3

4

5

Underrepresentation of women in Software Engineering (Numbers, reasons, solutions)

6

7

8

9

10

1

2

3

4

5

Biased data (Causes and effects in AI/Machine learning etc.)

6

7

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10

1

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10

Unconscious bias (In team work, IT HR etc.)

1

2

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10

Ethical software development / engineering ethics (Avoiding harmful software etc.)

1

2

3

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10

Unprofessional behavior (How people behave in customer/team work)

Diversity in problem solving/product development/innovations (The importance of diversity to the SE business/product development etc.)

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10

Some other approach or example to the diversity and inclusion in SE teaching

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10

I don't use any examples about diversity & inclusion in my course(s)

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10

2. Why you use or why you don't use diversity & inclusion examples in your course?

Have you added diversity & inclusion themes/cases/examples on your teaching by purpose or are there courses you are teaching those kind of that you can't find any angle to the topic?

500 merkkiä jäljellä

3. What other examples/approaches you use in your teaching about diversity & inclusion

Diversity & Inclusion can be approached in many ways (and we have really diverse amount of different SE courses!) and there can be so many things I did not listed below. So feel free to add here more different approaches to the diversity & inclusion in software engineering.

500 merkkiä jäljellä

4. Could you provide some examples how and where you use diversity & inclusion examples in your teaching - do you for example have some really good case you raise up in your lectures or do use use a diverse approach for example in the project courses?

Our aim is to collect best practices for other SE teachers as how they can provide D&I examples in their courses.

5. How important do you see that diversity and inclusion issues are approached in software engineering TEACHING

Scale 0 (not important at all) to 10 (Really important)

6. How important do you see that diversity and inclusion issues are raised up in your own software engineering faculty/team/school.

Scale 0 (not important at all) to 10 (Really important)

7. How satisfied you are on how diversity and inclusion issues are approached in your software engineering faculty/team/school.

Scale 0 (not happy at all) to 10 (Really happy)

8. Have there been some challenges in adding more info about D&I in SE teaching (Lack of information, negative attitudes from students etc.)?

9. Any other comments, thoughts about the topic etc.?

500 merkkiä jäljellä

Background questions

10. Gender (optional)

11. Teaching experience in years

- <5
- 5-10
- 11-20
- 20+